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Axon guidance receptor utilization during development of the CNS *in vivo*.

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We present here evidence of stage-specific axon guidance molecule function between E8-10 in the neuroepithelium, and in the neuroepithelium where an orientation to a facial structure exists. *Epha3* was activated in a developmental stage-specific pattern, only at day embryonic day 10. *Efna4* was activated contrarily, only in neuroepithelium at E8. A semaphorin was also selectively modulated here. We demonstrate evidence of active CNS axon guidance and wiring processes *in utero* and ability of whole transcriptome technologies to specifically identify repulsion and guidance cues mobilized that provide design to the human nervous system.